

Urban Reforms of Tanzimat: Early Urbanization and Transportation Practices in The Formation Process of Turkish Reconstruction System (1839-1908) in Bursa The First Capital City of Ottoman Empire

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Abstract—Bursa, since the establishment of the Ottoman Empire, being on the important trade roads and having a capital accumulation as a result of silk production, was one of the first cities of modernization activities applied. Bursa maintained its importance even during the Republican Period and became one of the most important cities of the country and today is the fourth biggest and the industrialized city in Turkey. Social, political, economical and cultural changes occurred with the reforms starting with the 1839 Edict of Tanzimat that aimed at modernizing the society and the government and centralizing the political power began in the Ottoman Empire. After the Tanzimat Reforms transformation of the city changed and planning processes began in Bursa according to the vision of Governors. The thresholds of the city are very important data for a sustainable planning for the city planners. Main aim of this study is to investigate the changes and transformations of the city according to the changes in the socio-economical and cultural properties for the city planners.

Keywords—Transportation, urbanization, Tanzimat reforms, modernization.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE formation process of Turkish reconstruction system is studied under the view of urbanization and transportation in the 19th century in the Ottoman period. Transportation and urbanization are related with each other. Developing sustainable planning strategies considering both past and future are very important for our common future.

The study includes four sections. After the introduction part, the historical and socio-economical structure are explained and the importance of the country is pointed out. In the following third section physical development and spatial structure of Bursa is examined. Finally at the last section the

previous sections are discussed and the conclusions are determined.

II. HISTORICAL AND SOCIO-ECONOMICAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE BURSA CITY

The city is one of the oldest settlements in the Marmara Region. The city had always maintained its importance from past till now because of its important location, history and socio-economical properties that will be explained in this section.

a) Historical development of the city

The historical information of Bursa before Ottomans is quite inadequate. The known history of the region, in which different civilizations lived, begins with Bithynians who settled in the region in the 7th century B.C and established an independent kingdom in 327 B.C.[1]. The Kingdom of Bithynia joined to the Roman Empire in 74 B.C. When the Roman Empire was divided in 395, the city of Bursa became a part of East Roman Empire. During his reign (525-565) the Emperor Justinianos founded a small thermal city in Pythia (Çekirge) by building a palace. During this era Bursa stood up both with its baths and its silk production.

Bursa was ruled as a type of principality *tekfurluk* -feudal land- for about thousand years on Byzantine Empire[2]. Annexed to the Ottoman Empire in 1326 by Sultan Orhan, the city of Bursa became the first Ottoman capital. During this era the city was built up and the most powerful governmental institution of the Ottoman Empire, the Palace was established in Bursa[3].

Ottoman Sultans located the high mounts of the city and respectively, Orhan, Hudavendigâr, Yıldırım, Yesil and Muradiye Kulliyes were constructed on these mounts (Figure 1). The area between these kulliyes consisted of the monumental structures and places constructed by statesmen through waqfs. With the conquest of Istanbul in 1453 the centre of government was moved to Istanbul. Consequently, scholars and senior soldiers close to the Sultan departed from Bursa as well. Until the mid 16th century, the city of Bursa was an international trade centre where silky, spicy and soft goods were sold through the western agents[5].

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Bursa was governed as a sanjak bounded to Anatolian Province of which centre was Kütahya after the governmental activities started to be carried out in İstanbul[6]. The unrest caused by Jelali Revolts, starting at the end of 16th century and continuing until the midst of 17th century while spreading all around Anatolia, influenced Bursa adversely [7].

Fig. 1 View from Tophane in Bursa in 1900's. [4].

Developing until the mid 16th century the city went through a relatively quiet period from the 17th century to the mid 19th century. During the Industrialization, in order to adjust to West, Westernizing movements started in Ottoman Empire in the 19th century. Social, political, economic and cultural changes occurred with the reforms starting with the 1839 Edict of Tanzimat that aimed at modernizing the society and the government and centralizing the political power began in the Ottoman Empire[8]. Bursa was one of the first cities of modernization activities applied in the 19th century because of its very important trade roads and silk production. The outbreak of the World War I in 1914, besides changing the international balances also unsettled the current structure of Bursa. With the outbreak of the war, groups building up the minority of the population, specially the Greeks (Rums) and the Armenians left the city.

Bursa in Republic Period went through a social, economic and physical process of change mostly with the foreign influences. Also in the Republican period Bursa maintained its importance due to the trade and being on the important transition conjunctions and being close to Istanbul. Especially, the Population Exchange Convention signed in 1923, has influenced Greek and Turkish societies by social, economic, political, cultural and demographic means. Bursa today, after 1960s, has become a very important center of industry leading in textile and automotive and is the fourth largest city in Turkey.

b) Socio-economic structure of Bursa

Silk production had always been important for the city in history. Starting with the Byzantine Period the silk production continued as silk trade in the 14th century and in this way silk textile industry flourished. For the raw material of silk industry was inadequate in Bursa, a major centre of silk trade in the 15th century; raw silk was imported from Iran. The economy of the city developed through the silk textile

industry depending on the raw silk[9]. At the end of the 16th century and at the beginning of the 17th century Ottoman cities generally had a population of 3.000 or 10.000 people, however Bursa was the only city of which population was over 50.000 people.

When the silk textile industry became important in Italy, Ottoman Empire made some adjustments ensuring Bursa to reach its heyday as a manufacture and trade centre[10]. As a result of these adjustments, Silk Road started to pass over Bursa and Tabriz-Bursa silk trade route became significant. Consequently, Bursa was provided with raw silk supplements and turned into a transfer centre of trade goods[11].

In the 14th century the only caravan route to Bursa for the goods from the East wasn't the Silk Road but also it was the Spice Road originated from Southeast Asia and passing over Bursa, Baghdad, Mosul and Halep. Thanks to the Spice Road, Bursa turned into a warehouse of all types of spices[5]. As understood from the number of the silk guilds, caravan trade made the specialized local manufacture develop[12].

Bursa, in order to be able to be a world trade centre, attracted the trade roads from the west and in the 15th century Bursa also became a domestic trade centre. Merchants from Florence, Genoa and Venice purchased silk in Bursa and they sold woollen products. In short, this procedure occurred as *the barter of the woollen products with the silk ones* [13]. In 1501 Mr. Maringhi, the commercial agent of the Medici family of Florence was in Koza Han, which showed the importance of the city[14].

Until the mid 16th century, the city of Bursa was an international trade centre where silky, spicy and soft goods were sold through the western agents[5]. As a result of the wars with Iran in 1520, the import of raw silk was forbidden and many weaving looms were closed down. In conclusion silk trade and silk textile industry started to deteriorate. Lasting from the end of the 16th century to the mid 17th century, Celali revolts affected Bursa negatively. The dissolution in state-owned land system and the changes in transportation and in the world trade caused Bursa to experience a quiet period.

Production of pure silk out of silkworm and production by weaving silk material and related trading activities, which all started in the 14th century and continued until the midst of the 16th century, have gone through a change in the 19th century as Europe become mechanized in weaving. The city of Bursa has not become a world trade center as it was in the 15th century, but has become a regional center of environmental economy which operates its agricultural production to raw material level according to the demands of the foreign markets and exports it to world market[15].

After the effects of the Industrial Reform, which had started in England in the 18th century and spread to other countries in a course of time and also felt in the Ottoman Empire; social, political, economic and cultural changes occurred with the reforms starting with the 1839 Edict of Tanzimat that aimed at modernizing the society and the government and centralizing the political power[8]. New places of change and transformation have started to be formed. Due to the production and consumption relationships urban culture, urban life style and urbanization got into a reshaping process

and the traces of this change can clearly be observed in Bursa within the modernization period in Bursa.

III. PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT AND SPATIAL STRUCTURE OF BURSA

a) Physical development and spatial structure of Bursa between 14th and 16th centuries

Before the Ottoman Empire, the city consisted of the citadel, the khaneh citadel where the Tekfur Palace was, and Down Citadel- *Kale Altı*-[5]. It has been understood that in the residential area restricted by the city walls there were no public buildings and no manufacture and trade structures required by urbanization.(Fig. 2)

Fig. 2 The texture of the city and the citadel in Suphi Beg Map dated 1862.[4].

The old city was restricted by the city walls and the new city started to be built up 200-300 m. northwest of this area on an empty area. Orhan Gazi made mosques, madrasahs, khans and bazaars constructed outside the citadel in Bursa and thus he founded important waqfs. The city continued to grow up topographically in the east-west direction by the construction of commercial activities such as bedesten, arasta bridge, bazaars, open market places and stores on an area outside the citadel Figure 3. Around the bedesten different occupational groups formed a separate unit. It was clearly seen that in Bursa market square streets developed around the bedesten and were directed to the doors of the bedesten. Around the bedesten specialized streets in manufacture, trade and service activities appeared. Besides commercial structures there monumental buildings such as mosques, public baths and madrasahs were constructed in the region.

The khans started to be built up so that the collection and the delivery of the caravan trade goods, starting in the 14th century and continuing until the mid 16th century, could be ensured, a shopping environment could be created and the necessity for exchanging important products and for bargaining in closed places could be fulfilled. As the number of the khans increased in Bursa commercial city center, a cooperation began and on the roads connected the khans, new bazaars were opened in the form of guilds whose production and selling functions differentiated and specialized in

particular products with the philosophy of *ahilik* so the people producing and marketing the same goods gathered in order of guild in particular places and streets so the khaneh and the outer places became identical[2]. As can be understood from the names in the registers, every tradesman took part in a different bazaar or on a different street. The bazaars were either formed in the style of the shops surrounding a street or built as a distinct place. In this sense, the bazaars are examined under the headings of food trade, textile, woodwork, mine decoration (handwork), leather manufacturing and the others. It is known that most of the bazaars are occupied on Uzun Çarşı which was the oldest part of the city centre, starting to be built up with Emir Khan.

Fig. 3 The historical evolution of commercial buildings in the Khans Region at the end of the 16th century[16].

Open markets districts in Bursa ensured the food consumed by the city dwellers from the agricultural areas around the city and made some products needing a specialized approach produced and marketed in the city. The open bazaars set up on some certain days of the week near the mosques or small mosques provided the daily food need of the people in the city.

In the Region of Khans shops were the largest in number and the simplest in style and their construction materials were the most varied. The shops could be on a roofless street or under a covered bazaar in a row in an in or in a bedesten[17].

Evliya Çelebi mentioned that there were 9000 shops in Uzun Çarşı (Uzun Bazaar). After the second half of the 16th century, because of the socio-economic and political structure a new construction was not added to the city structure in Bursa. It can be observed that important changes in the physical and social structure did not happen in Bursa and that the city preserved its stable structure in the 17th century. Because of the necessity for the defence of the city against Celali Revolts started in Anatolian, a protection wall was built up and the transportation in the city and the construction process happened inside these borders.

In the city of Bursa market square was the focal point and the districts were located around the commercial center and connected with a road network to the center. The commercial center wasn't only a shopping centre but also it was the heart of the city where people worshipped, gathered and also the

place where social decisions were made for the public; and all social and cultural activities were carried out with its mosque, its khan for the travellers, its bedesten for shopping, its madrasahs, and its baths where the water and the green came together.

b) Physical development and spatial structure of Bursa in the 19th century

During the Industrialization, in order to adjust to West, Westernizing movements started in Ottoman Empire [18]. Especially, during the period of Sultan Abdülaziz in 1861, by assigning Ahmet Vefik Pasha, who was charged as the ambassador of Paris and had the chance of observing the great changes made by Baron Haussmann in the city, as the governor of Bursa, the establishment of “a new and modern Ottoman city” was provided. Thus, almost all the Tanzimat period buildings built in Bursa which was a totally collapsed city after the 1855 earthquake mark the same period of governorship of Ahmet Vefik Pasha [19].

The city of Bursa in the 19th century displays a spatial structure of a religious-economic center with residential areas, streets and suburbs located around it as well as a formation of an area where with culture and administration buildings, different trade buildings like banks, blocks of offices, bureaus, silk fabrics locate together around a center formed by khans, a bazaar where antiques and valuables are sold, traditional bazaars. Therefore, new wide roads, combining modern public locations and locations like city hall, government hall, theatre, schools, post office, hospital, Osmanlı Bank, shops, warehouses, blocks of offices, silk fabrics, hotels, police office and clock tower, are built.

In the center of the city Bursa, in order to store and dry cocoon, as trade and industry buildings Nuri Pasha Cocoon Warehouse, Şark Dühan (tobacco) Warehouse and on the northeast of Sarrafiye Madrasah Resulzade Dye-house, are built on Hamidiye (Cumhuriyet) Street, and also as a reflection of new economic relationships on physical structure, Osmanlı Bank on the southeast of Orhan Mosque, which is located in the direct domain, is built. Single storey buildings on Uzun Bazaar, at the end of 19th century and towards the beginning of the 20th century, have been converted to single or group shops of stone buildings which get sun light from one direction and are not higher than five-six meters.

Trade buildings undergoing such a change has also occurred in administration buildings. The inner fort located in the citadel representing the old administration center and the Government Hall representing the new administration system is nowadays built in the area where Atatürk Statue is and the City Hall, symbol of local administration, which even today is used for the same purpose, was built on the east of Orhan Mosque. The City Hall, the symbol of local administration, is located near the main road between the Government Hall, the symbol of provincial management, and Ulucami (The Great Mosque), the symbol of the former grandeur of the capital. The Post Office was restructured near Hacılar and Kara Seyh Mosques [19], and on the west of Hamidiye Street and on the northeast corner of the street a police station and fountain was

built. As a result, the influence of the West culture within the new economic relationships brought for the cultural structures like theaters and entertainment places with it. After Istanbul, the first settled theatre in Turkey was established by Governor Ahmet Vefik Pasha in 1879 between the block of offices aligned with Ziraat Bank across the Statue of Atatürk [20].

After the fire in 1854 and 1863, new urbanism plans with the the right angle principles were used for the re-establishment of districts. The Armenian Region at the east of the city in Setbaşı was damaged from the big fire and was reconstructed with the principles of the grille system. The most important axis of this plan started from the Setbaşı Bridge, passed by the Armenian Church and ended at the School of Sericulture and named as *İpekçilik* Sericulture Street[19].

At the same time, residences for foreign merchants and the French Consulate building were near the Cilimboz stream. However, domestic silk merchants, focusing on *İpekçilik*-Sericulture- area, formed a residential area for a group with high incomes.

c) Transportation Process in the Formation of Turkish Reconstruction System

Industrial Revolution changed the economic structure of European countries in the 19th century. During this period trade activities between European countries and the cities of Anatolia were observed. Within the change of production relationships in the 19th century, related to the silk industry, industrial areas of silk fabrics were formed near the Gökdere and Cilimboz streams in the city.

Fig. 4 The locations of Railway Stations in Bursa City Map, dated 1921[21].

These developments affected the transportation system since the second half of 19th century in Bursa. Economic value created abroad to be reached in the area, agricultural and industrial raw materials needed to provide transport by the region to Lyon. For this purpose in 1892 Mudanya-Bursa railway was constructed in order to transport the raw materials and the semi-finished products, produced in Bursa, to Lyon, France. In a sense, silk industry brought for the construction of a railway in the city. Produced yarn in the filature factories

in Bursa was transported from Mudanya Port to the Port of Marseilles then Lyon (Fig. 4 and 5).

Fig. 5 The train in Bursa [22].

It is not possible to mention a holistic planning strategy in the 19th century. However, within the vision of the governors who have the authorization of administration on behalf of the government, partial and quite intuitive planning efforts, aiming to find an answer to the changing problems of the day, were observed[23]. Commerce, which spread to a quite large area in the second half of the 16th century, has become an area limited with Atatürk Street (Palace and Government) on the south, İnönü Street on the east, and Cumhuriyet Street (Hamidiye) on the north at the end of the 19th century and at beginning of the 20th century as a result of the urbanism projects which were started by Governor Ahmet Vefik Pasha (1865) and continued by Ahmet Münir Pasha (1891-1897) and Mümtaz Reşit Pasha (1903-1906).(Fig. 6)

Fig. 6. The roads at the end of the 19th century and at the beginning of the 20th century (Bağbancı, K.Ö., 2007:181)

IV. GENERAL EVALUATION AND CONCLUSION

At the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century, commercial region had become a central with the limited borders by the planning projects. The changing of communication system had strengthened the region in the

state town, new wide roads for a suitable traffic were made, but had caused destroying of many historical monuments. Related to the consumption habits changed with the modernization process in 19th century, new trade centers were built and connected to the change of the socio-cultural life; new administrative and cultural buildings were constructed.

With the modernization process in 19th century, new trade centers were built and connected to the change of the socio-cultural life; new administrative and cultural buildings were constructed. New wide roads for a suitable traffic were made, Bursa-Mudanya railway was opened to transport the produced silk to France and new industry areas were formed after production became mechanized.

As a conclusion after the urbanization and transportation practices the texture of the city had changed and the city center became a limited area after the urbanization and transportation process in the city. Changes and transformations are inevitable in the cities. But the important view of this study is to determine the thresholds of the city, and the important data for the city planners.

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